

Impact of high-yielding varieties on rice production in Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil

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New varieties released in southern Brazil since 1970 (see table) are mostly short-statured and adapted to climatic

conditions. The harvest index has increased and yield potential, grain quality, and adaptability have promoted farmer acceptance.

Among the varieties, Bluebelle and BR-IRGA409 are early, BR-IRGA410 and BR-IRGA411 are medium duration, and BR-IRGA407 is late maturing. Breeding programs have focused on yield improvement, grain

quality, cold tolerance, and disease resistance. High yielders with durations of 109-147 d were identified and isolated. Early and medium-duration varieties were selected indirectly.

In 1984, high-yielding rice varieties represented about 98% of 704,000 ha in Rio Grande do Sul, with yields of 4.5 t/ha. BR-IRGA lines alone covered about 70% of this area. *ℒ*

High-yielding varieties released in Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil, 1970-85.

Variety	Origin	Cross-combination	Released		Approximate yield (t/ha)	Maturity (d)	Grain type ^b	Height (cm)	Area planted 1983/84 season (thousand ha)
			By ^a	Year					
Bluebelle	USA	CI 9122/Century Patna 231/CI 92 14	IPEAS	1970	4.7	109	LS	91	195.1
IRGA 407	Brazil	Selected from local variety	EEA/IRGA	1971	4.3	147	LB	130	3.1
BR-IRGA 409	CIAT/IRRI	P790-B4-4-1T (IR930-2/IR665-31-1-4)	EMBRAPA/IRGA	1978	6.1	110	LS	100	457.6
BR-IRGA 410	CIAT/IRRI	P798-B4-4-1T (IR930-53/IR665-31-2)	EMBRAPA/IRGA	1980	6.7	130	LS	110	35.2
BR-IRGA 411	Brazil	Dawn/IRGA407	EMBRAPA/IRGA	1985	4.1	130	LS	103	—

^aIPEAS = South Agricultural Research Institute now EMBRAPA; EEA = IRGA's Experimental Station; IRGA = Rio-grandense Rice Institute; EMBRAPA = Federal Agricultural Research System. ^bLS = long slender; LB = long bold.

Rice strain R243-3223 promising for lowland rainfed conditions in eastern Madhya Pradesh, India

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Agronomic conditions in Madhya Pradesh limit the adoption of typical semidwarf varieties. These conditions include dependence on the monsoon, with only 20% irrigation coverage; broadcast crop establishment, which gives low plant populations despite high seed rates; predominance of long duration varieties, which often suffer from failure of September rains; low fertilizer consumption; and lack of varieties with multiple resistance.

Breeding objectives have been modified toward developing semitall varieties of shorter duration that respond to moderate levels of fertilizer and are tolerant of commonly occurring

Table 1. Yield of R243-3223 and IR36 in Madhya Pradesh, India.

Location	Strain	Yield (t/ha)			
		1982	1983	1984	Mean
Waraseoni	R243	4.0	4.1	4.3	4.1
	IR36	3.7	3.7	2.2	3.2
Rewa	R243	4.0	2.9	2.4	3.1
	IR36	2.3	2.8	2.7	2.6
Bagwai	R243	3.7	2.9	3.3	3.3
	IR36	3.7	2.2	3.5	3.1
Raipur (Pathology)	R243	5.9	5.0	4.7	5.2
	IR36	5.8	4.9	4.4	5.0
Raipur (Breeding)	R243	3.4	3.0	2.6	3.0
	IR36	3.2	3.1	2.8	3.1
Jagdalpur	R243	4.4	4.5	6.1	5.0
	IR36	5.0	2.7	5.8	4.5
Jabalpur	R243	2.5	4.3	3.6	3.5
	IR36	3.4	4.2	3.3	3.6
Bilaspur	R243	—	—	4.0	4.0
	IR36	—	—	3.5	3.5
Mean	R243	4.0	3.8	3.8	3.9
	IR36	3.9	3.4	3.5	3.6

diseases and pests.

A new rice strain R243-3223 (IET8756) was derived from the cross IR36/IR2053-521. Cross IR7516 was received from IRRI in the F₂. This

strain has given higher yields than IR36 and Safrí 17, the most popular semidwarf and tall varieties of the region (Table 1). Its 100 ± 10 cm stature results in better germination capacity under